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Correction: Bacterial cellulose–hyaluronan nanocomposite biomaterials as wound dressings for severe skin injury repair

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Correction for 'Bacterial cellulose–hyaluronan nanocomposite biomaterials as wound dressings for severe skin injury repair' by Ying Li et al., *J. Mater. Chem. B*, 2015, 3, 3498–3507.

The authors regret that an incorrect FE-SEM image was used in Fig. 4 (0.2% HA, bottom) of their original manuscript. The corrected version of Fig. 4 is shown below. The caption for the figure remains unchanged.

Fig. 4 Light microscopy images (upper) and FE-SEM images (bottom) showing the growth and morphology of primary human fibroblast cells attached to the scaffold. Round cells are indicated by an arrow (←) while spindle shape cells are indicated by an arrow (→). The light microscopy images and FE-SEM images were recorded at 200× magnifications (scale bar is 100 μm, upper) and 1000 magnifications (scale bar is 100 μm, bottom), respectively.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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